

Welcome to the 2nd volume of the EU-HIP Newsletter!

We are excited to present to you the second volume of our Newsletter which keeps you up-to-date with the EU-HIP project and beyond. Building upon the foundation laid in our first volume, which offered an introduction to the work behind EU-HIP and HERA, we now shift our focus to the projects Landscape Analysis through the lens of the first in-depth country visit to Croatia. In addition to that, you will get insights from the HERA Symposium held in April and meet the project EU-WISH.

Let's start!

Landscape assessment within EU-HIP

A baseline activity of the EU-HIP project is to perform a Landscape Analysis of countries' IT systems, in relation to public health surveillance and medical countermeasures (MCM) to support threat assessment and crisis management across Europe. The priority areas are pathogens with high pandemic potential (PHPP), antimicrobial resistance (AMR), and chemical, biological, radiological, and nuclear (CBRN) threats, as well as appropriate medical countermeasures, such as medicinal products, medical devices, and personal protective equipment (PPE). As a part of the Landscape Analysis, in-depth country visits are being performed in a selected number of countries, to gain detailed insights into the countries' IT systems for health threat detection and assessment.

Country visit to Croatia

The first country visit was performed in Croatia at the end of 2023. Colleagues from Sciensano have been responsible for conducting interviews and writing the final report. The country visit was organized with the support of the Croatian National Public Health. Eight in-person interviews were performed over two days.

Getting deeper insight: meet Croatia!

Interviewed Stakeholders		
Croatian Institute of Public Health		
Division for Health Informatics and Biostatistics	Division for Toxicology	Division for Microbiology
School of Medicine, University of Zagreb Department of Environmental and Occupational Health and Sports Medicine		
University Hospital for Infectious Diseases Department of Clinical Microbiology		
Ministry of the Interior Civil Protection Directorate, radiological and nuclear, preparedness and response		
Ministry of Health		

For every priority area defined by HERA we have mapped key actors and stakeholders networks, described digital infrastructures and systems and given an overview of the legislation and strategy.

One interesting case is the data collection for infectious diseases in Croatia through the Registry of Infectious Diseases. Current legislation regarding the protection of the population from infectious diseases lays down that every case of any disease present on the list, which is updated regularly, needs to be reported. It can be done either by paper form or with electronic reporting via the Central Health Information System of the Republic of Croatia (CEZIH).

The Registry of Infectious Diseases is part of the National Public Health Information System (NAJS) which includes multiple registries and other sources of data, structured as shown below.

This is just one of the many cases covered in the report. Others include reporting of antimicrobial resistance, the structure of strategic commodity stocks and many more.

If this is an interesting topic for you - go ahead and open the [Country visit report available on Zenodo](#).

HERA Symposium April 2024

On April 4th and 5th, key stakeholders from across the European Union attended in Brussels the HERA Symposium. The event focused on advancing laboratory and digital capacities for health emergency preparedness and response to fortify Europe's threat detection capacities and public health intelligence in relation to medical countermeasures. During the two days experts, policymakers, and stakeholders from diverse disciplines, ranging from healthcare institutions to governmental bodies, research organizations, and academia met to enhance collaboration, knowledge sharing, and leveraging innovative solutions to safeguarding public health amidst future crises.

Representatives from the EU-HIP project have participated in this event, sharing knowledge and experiences from our consortium with other attendees. Breakout and case study sessions helped conclude that the cooperation between different stakeholders and active collaboration between projects is mandatory to fortify Europe's healthcare capabilities in face of evolving health emergencies.

To read more about this topic read the [news announcement](#).

Meet EU-WISH!

As stated in the previous chapter, cooperation between existing initiatives can give fruitful results beyond the scope of individual actions. One of the projects also presented on the HERA Symposium is EU-WISH - a Joint Action under the EU4Health programme, which supports the policy priority of strengthening the European Union's capacity to prevent, prepare for and respond rapidly to serious cross-border health threats.

The focus of EU-WISH is to support activities to strengthen and improve national capacities for wastewater public health surveillance by enhancing knowledge exchange and sharing best practices based on scientific evidence.

To learn more about the project you can visit their [official website](#).